

ELABORATION OF CACTUS FIBRE COMPOSITE LAMINATE AND CHARACTERISATION UNDER STATIC AND FATIGUE LOADING

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SUMMARY

In this work we present the results of a new method to extract cactus fibres for novel laminate biocomposites, together with the chemical characterisation of the biofibres. The composites are mechanically tested under uniaxial, fatigue tensile and bending loading. The cyclic fatigue investigations are related only to the cactus fibre/polyester composites laminate under flexural loading. The damage mechanisms after a static and cyclic loading are described and discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The search for new materials with innovative mechanical properties and sustainable sourcing is of paramount importance in today's technological and economic landscape. Ecological concerns have resulted in a renewed interest in natural materials, and such issues as recyclability and environmental safety have become increasingly important for the introduction of new materials and products. Structural polymer composites are traditionally utilizing man-made fibres (such as glass or carbon fibres) as reinforcement, but environmental issues have generated a considerable interest in natural fibres [1, 2]. At this moment, designing for recycling or in a somewhat broader perspective, eco-design, is becoming a philosophy that is applied to more and more materials and products. It is for these reasons that natural fibres based on lignocellulose can be considered as an interesting environmentally safe alternative for the use of glass fibres as reinforcement in engineering polymeric materials [2]. The use of natural fibres has many advantages, such as being derived from a renewable resource, requiring low energy inputs in their manufacture, and being easily disposed of at the end of their life cycle by composting or by recovery of their calorific value in a furnace, something not possible with glass fibres. In spite of the many advantages of natural fibres, they also exhibit some undesirable characteristics. High moisture absorption, low thermal resistance, and highly anisotropic properties are the main disadvantages associated with natural fibres [3].

The objective of this work is the extraction of fibres from plants using an economically viable method for engineering structural applications [4]. Different techniques have been developed in the past, one of them consisting in immersing the sample in water (dates fibres), while other extraction techniques involve chemical solutions like the alkenes [5]. This paper describes the extraction of cactus fibres and the manufacturing of a composite laminate using the plat fibres extracted, together with the determination of their chemical characteristics. A mechanical characterization of the fibre and

composite is carried out using uniaxial and fatigue tests under tensile and bending loading.

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

2.1. Extraction of cactus fibres

A new method is proposed to extract cactus fibres in order to separate the layers from the calcium oxalate (Figure 1). The method consists on burying the trunk under 30 cm depth of earth during 15 days; allowing the calcium oxalate fermentation and therefore making the extraction of the cactus fibre layers easy. The fibres are then washed with water and air dried with outdoor exposure. In figure 1, A, B and C are the locations of the extract cactus fibre from the trunk on the centre, middle and at external part respectively. The fibres are extracted from an old racket (about 50 years) from which one can observe the modification of the architecture according to its maturation (Figure 2). The more one approaches the end of the cactus trunk (maturate fibre), the more the second body becomes denser, providing segments as large as those of the first body, making therefore difficult to distinguish the first body from the second.

Figure 1. Transverse section of a cactus trunk, a) before the burying, b) after 15 days of the burying.

Figure 2 Fibres extracted from various locations of a cactus trunk located on the centre, middle and at external part respectively a), b) and c).

2.2. Fibre chemical characterization

In order to highlight the cactus fibre degradation according to the extraction method, an investigation is carried out by infra-red spectrometry of two fibres, one extracted by the new method proposed in this work, and another fibre naturally extracted (left in their

racket until the dryness of calcium oxalate). The tests are carried out at the industrial analysis laboratory and genius of materials of chemistry of Guelma University.

Figure 3a represents the infra-red spectrum of the extracted fibre by burying proposed in this work, which is similar to the one of natural fibres present in open literature (wood fibre [6]). On the other hand there is a remarkable change in the chemical composition of fibre extracted naturally compared to that extracted by the new method proposed in this work as shown in figure 3-b. The burying fibre presents the signals characteristic of lignocellulose, which include broad band of the groups of hydroxyl of cellulose (O-H) at 3271.55 cm^{-1} [7], and the double connections carbonyls (C=C) correspond to a peak of 1646.7 cm^{-1} [8]. These two peaks are not present in the spectrum figure 3.b, which shows the modification on the level of the chemical composition of fibre due to the fibres extraction mode.

Figure 3 Infra-red spectrum a) cactus fibre present work b) fibre extracted naturally c) sisal of Mexico fibre [6].

2.3. Composite cactus/polyester elaborations

The composite plates have been manufactured, using moulding technique at low pressure. The composites are impregnated at room temperature (18 to 20°C) and the resin is catalyzed and hardened in proportions ranging between 1 and 1.5% in mass. The plates are maintained at low pressure for 24 hours before to be released from the mould, in order to be polymerised. Mass rate of the fibre laminates M_f is determined by the weight method, the fibre rate is the relationship between the mass of fibres and the plate mass. This measurement makes it possible to obtain an average fibre rate of the plate.

2.4 Experimental setup

Tensile, flexural static and cyclic loading tests are carried out according to ASTM D79 standard using universal testing machine ZWICK ROELLE Z005 type, which has a load cell having a capacity of 5 kN. The static tests are carried out using a speed of 2

mm/min. The fatigue tests are carried out in control displacement with a sinusoidal wave form of 1.5 Hz frequency. A mean displacement (d_{mean}) is maintained constant and equal to 50% of displacement to static failure (d_r). Several loading levels r_d ($r_d = d_{\text{max}}/d_r$) representing the ratio of maximum displacement to the displacement at static rupture are considered, varying from 0.95 to 0.60. The specimens tested used in fatigue tests are identical to those used in the case of static ones.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extracted cactus fibres are tested in axial tension according to standard AFNOR 57-101. The tests are repeated for three different trunks. The cactus fibres architecture 1 has the best mechanical behaviour compared to architectures 2 and 3, according to the results obtained from the evolution of the stress-strain curves for monotonous tension loading (Figure 4). This behaviour is due to the fibre location in the trunk; the fibres having architecture 1 are extracted from the external part of a trunk, which provides porous fibres with smaller cells, and therefore higher density compared to architectures 2 and 3. The latter two topologies are related to fibres extracted respectively in the middle and the centre of the trunk. The curve stress-strain of the cactus fibre of architecture 1 has a similar shape than that found in the literature for natural fibres such as the flax [9] and the cactus [10].

Table 1 illustrates the mechanical properties of the three architectures tested. The elastic modulus is calculated according to ASTM standard with a slope between (0.5 to 1)% of the strain.

Figure 4 Experimental Stress-strain curves for the three investigated architectures.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of various cactus fibres subjected to uni-axial tension loading.

	σ_{failure} [MPa]	$\varepsilon_{\text{failure}}$ [%]	E_L [MPa]
Architecture 1	27	2,60	1100,45
Architecture 2	7,75	2,20	585,47
Architecture 3	10	1,90	705,93
Cactus fibre [5]	27,30	2,90	1168

Where: σ_{failure} , $\varepsilon_{\text{failure}}$ and E_L are respectively the stress and the strain at failure and the longitudinal module in tension loading.

According to Table 1 one notices that the mechanical properties vary depending on the cactus fibre architecture, knowing that the modification of the architecture is due to the maturation of the plant. Further more, the results obtained are in very good agreement with these obtained by Malainine et al. [10].

3.1. Mechanical behaviours of the composite laminates (cactus/polyester) under tension static loading

The tensile tests were carried out until the failure of the specimens tested at speed of 2 mm/min and the dimensions of the specimens are prepared according to AFNOR 57-101 Standard and the specimens are cut out in the direction of fibres and have respectively length, width and thickness of $l = 250$ mm, $b = 25$ mm and $h = 2.5$ mm. The mass fraction of fibres (m_f) is taken 25% this is in agreement with the literature [11-12]. The stress-strain curves (Figure 5) are characterized by two phases: the first one non linear until about 0.3 % of the strain corresponding to the slip of the specimen's and the second one linear until the total rupture. The longitudinal module was calculated with a slope between (0.5 to 1) % of the strain, and these characteristics obtained are presented in Table 2.

Figure 5 Stress/strain curves of cactus/polyester laminate composite with a mass fraction of 25% subjected to monotonous tension uniaxial loading.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of composite laminated cactus/polyester loaded in tension in the fibre direction.

Specimens	σ_{failure} [MPa]	$\varepsilon_{\text{failure}}$ [%]	E_L [MPa]
1	15.70	1.35	1361.1
2	15.73	1.35	1351.3
3	15.40	1.21	1559.7
4	16.28	1.23	1631.7
Average	15.78	1.29	1476.0

Although the specimens are cut out from the same plate the results obtained (Young modulus, stress strain) are characterized by a dispersions between the various specimens tested (Figure 5). The origin of these dispersions observed for the Young modulus is due to the strong anisotropy of the fibres [13] and can be related to fibre volume fraction [14], which is an uncontrollable factor considering the morphology of the cactus fabric.

While, the dispersion in the stress and the strain values can due directly to the cavities in the matrix, and the variety of the fibre architecture's [15].

3.2 Mechanical behaviours of the composite laminates (cactus/polyester) subjected to static 3-point bending

The bending tests are carried out according to ASTM D79 standard at test speed of 2 mm/min. The load/displacement curve of a composite cactus/polyester under 3-point bending presented on Figure 6 is characterized by a linear behaviour until a displacement of 2 mm corresponding to the initiation of the cracks on the matrix (resin). The increase in the load causes the development of the cracks and a behaviour staircase of the curve load/displacement is recorded until the brutal rupture of the specimens. This behaviour has been observed by Hepworth and Smith [16] in the case of the tendon fibres pearl glue.

Figure 6 Load/displacement curve of a composite cactus/polyester, subjected to monotonous 3 point bending.

The mechanical properties of all specimens cactus/polyester tested in 3 point bending are presented in table 3. The results obtained show that there is a variation in the properties at failure (stress/displacement) as well as a weak variation in the elasticity modulus. Dispersions recorded for the stress and displacement at failure under 3-point bending is powerfully related to the variation of the fibre architectures in particular the vicinity of the zone under the central support i.e. places with low fibre in the specimens tested. The dispersion observed for the module in bending is generally related to the anisotropy of fibre as it was already explained previously for the tensile tests.

Table 3 Mechanical properties in 3 point bending of a composite cactus/polyester.

Specimens	σ_{failure} [MPa]	d_{failure} [mm]	E_f [MPa]
1	86,50	6,53	8329,5
2	86,41	6,49	8463,1
3	94,43	6,57	8262,5
4	82,40	6,74	8246,3
average	87,45	6,6	8325,1±5

3.3 Mechanical behaviours of a cactus/polyester composite laminates under flexural cyclic loading

The follow-up of the rigidity loss (F/F_0) constitutes one of the methods most used to follow the progression of the damage by cyclic loading of the composites [17]. During these tests, we recorded the evolution of the maximum load F according to the number of cycles N . The force F is normalized by that obtained one at the first cycle F_0 . Figure 7 show the evolution of the F/F_0 versus the number of cycles N in semi-logarithmic scale of a cactus/polyester composite material with mass fraction m_f of 25%, for the various loading levels (r_d). For a high loading levels, corresponding to a large amplitudes, the fatigue strength is very short and the total rupture of the specimens is obtained for a few hundreds of cycles for $r_d = 0.95$ or 0.90 . However, for a low loading levels corresponding to small amplitudes, the mechanisms of damage are activated with a very slow propagation and the fatigue strength is very important. Indeed, at one million cycle the rupture is only partial for $r_d = 0.60$.

Figure 7 Rigidity loss F/F_0 versus the number of cycles of a cactus/polyester composite for various loading levels r_d .

3.3.1 S-N Curves

Figure 8 represents the S-N curves using different rupture criteria N_5 , N_{10} and N_{50} and the variation of the loading levels r_d versus the number of cycles N can be described by linear equation [13]

$$r_d = 1 - K \log N \quad (1)$$

Where: K the slope of the straight line of the fitted experimental data.

The endurance diagrams give the evolution of the loading level (r_d) according to the number of cycles by using the criteria of failure N_5 , N_{10} and N_{50} . The analysis of the results obtained, show a dispersion of the values of the fatigue life. However, it arises that the results converges towards the unit for low numbers of cycles; what shows that when the loading level is neared to that of the in static's failure. The rupture of the specimens is obtained as of the first cycles for high loading levels, on the other hand for low levels of loading, the failure is obtained for numbers of very high cycles [18].

Figure 8 S-N Curves of cactus/polyester using criteria N_5 , N_{10} and N_{50} .

3.3.2. Fracture topographies

The observation of the fracture topographies with microscopic of the specimens subjected to a cyclic loading (figure 9 a and b) shows that the rupture of material passes by three mechanisms of rupture during the fatigue test in 3-point bending. Initially rupture of the matrix (figure 18a), followed by the damage interface (separation matrix) fibre and finally the rupture of fibres (figure 18b). On the other hand this phenomenon of rupture of the interface by separation matrix fibre does not exist on the specimens subjected to a monotonous 3-point bending.

Figure 9. Fracture topography of specimens subjected to cyclic 3-point bending.

4. CONCLUSION

The natural fibres have many advantages compared to synthetic fibres (low costs, renewable resource, biodegradation, specific mechanical properties important (resistance and rigidity). On the other hand, the non knowledge of the various types of natural fibres and there mechanical behaviour can be a big disadvantages on their industrial development.

A novel method of cactus fibres extraction is used; it consists on burying the trunk of the cactus in the earth which supports the fermentation of calcium oxalate and consequently the layers of fibres become easy to separate. The tissue of cactus changes their morphology during the maturation of this plant. The technique of spectrometry shows that the fibres extracted with the new method preserves better its physico-chemical characteristics, compared to that fibre extracted.

According to the tests carried out on three architectures of cactus fibre extracted from the trunk on the centre, middle and at external part, one can conclude that the elasticity modulus varies with the located extracted fibre and the architecture of the cactus fibre influences considerably the mechanical properties of the elaborate composite.

The load/displacement on tensile test on the composite cactus/polyester shows that the behaviour occur on two phases: the first one non linear until about 0.3 % of the strain corresponding to the slip of the specimen's and the second one linear until the total rupture. On the other hand the behaviour on 3-point bending the first phase is linear followed by a nonlinear part and the development of the cracks lead to staircase behaviour of the curve load/displacement until the brutal rupture of the specimens.

The results obtained by the follow-up of the rigidity loss (F/F_0) in fatigue test of composite cactus/polyester until the rupture of the specimens, proceeds in three phases, a brutal degradation is notice for the first which is related to the fragility of the matrix, the second phase is characterized by a very slow reduction, corresponding to the near total of the fatigue life of the specimens and finally the redaction of F/F_0 is accelerates until the rupture of the specimens for the last phase. The observations with microscopic permitted to highlight the mechanism of damage and shows that the mechanisms of rupture of material requested in fatigue, are different in static 3-point bending.

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